

Mobilise-D Scoping Review: Abstract Screening – Round 2

Instructions

- In the second round of abstract review, references can be excluded ONLY for the following reasons, which were agreed upon by the Parkinson disease area team following the initial round of abstract screening.
- If the article does not meet the following exclusion criteria, it **must** be included (even if you would not have included it in the initial round of review).
- If you think an additional exclusion criterion should be added to this stage, please state it in “other”

Question 1: Are any of the following exclusion criteria met? (Select all that apply)

Exclusion Criteria	Description, Factors eligible for exclusion
A Study does not present original data	Reviews, editorials, comments, etc.
B Entire study population receives deep brain stimulation	e.g., studying the impact of DBS on gait, comparing two DBS frequencies
C Fewer than 10 participants per study arm	
D Only excluded clinical walking assessments were studied	ONLY exclude if the study was limited to the following <i>uninstrumented</i> tests: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-reported walking time/distance • 6MWT/12MWT, 20+ minute walk distance, 400m walk time, etc. • Incremental or endurance shuttle walk test • TUG • Dynamic gait index • Other questionnaire-based or subjective assessment of gait, or studies that clearly do not assess gait
E Gait speed test is conducted on a track shorter than 4 meters	
F Protocol or registration for an INTERVENTIONAL trial that uses a GaWP as an outcome	<i>These protocols will be indexed for future analysis</i>
G Non-interventional or non-relevant protocol or registration	The following protocols are excluded: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-interventional studies • Systematic/Scoping Reviews • Interventional studies not using GaWPs as endpoints
H Population does not meet disease-specific eligibility criteria (i.e., excluded disease subtype)	Exclude the following disease subtypes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Atypical parkinsonian syndromes, • drug-induced parkinsonism, • vascular parkinsonism, • progressive supranuclear palsy, • multiple system atrophy, • corticobasal syndrome, • dementia with lewy bodies • Any other disease area (clearly not PD)
I Animal or in-vitro (non-human) studies	
J Other (please explain)	Any suggested criteria will be discussed by the group

****If you are unsure, please be conservative and include the study in full-text review.**